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*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

Научно-исследовательский институт «Физики резонансных ядерных реакций» является научным учреждением, осуществляющим фундаментальные, прикладные научные исследования и инновационные разработки в области науки, техники, культуры и просвещения.

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PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL – LEGAL ACTIVE CIVIC COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article highlights the fact that the most important factor in the reforms being implemented in the education system of our independent state is the upbringing of a socially active, harmonious young generation, and the pedagogical and psychological aspects of developing socially and legally active civic competence in students.

Keywords: student, active citizenship, competence, pedagogical and psychological aspects, educational institution.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his speech at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly on September 23, 2017, touched upon the issue of youth: «More than half of the population of our country is made up of young people. In our republic, great work is being done to ensure that every young man and woman takes their rightful place in society and realizes their potential.» [1]

The five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019, also emphasize the role and importance of educational institutions in educating socially active students and youth. Because these «five most important initiatives» include further strengthening attention to youth, involving them in culture, art, physical education and sports, developing skills in using information technologies among youth, promoting reading among the youth of our country, and ensuring women’s employment» – tasks that play an important role in the development of socially active civic competencies for

the country's future, as well as in the upbringing of mature, well-rounded youth.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, touched upon the issue of youth: «Since we have set ourselves the goal of transforming Uzbekistan into a developed country, we will achieve this not only through rapid reforms, science, education, and innovation. To do this, first of all, we need to educate a new generation of cadres who will take the initiative as reformers, think strategically, are knowledgeable, and qualified,» and in the context of this address, the most important problem facing educators is to develop the young generation studying in higher education institutions as socially active citizens. [2]

In the context of the reforms being implemented in our country, research has been conducted on the problem of training the young generation as mature personnel with high intellectual, socially active, initiative, spiritual and moral potential. The research touched upon such issues as the culture of a healthy lifestyle and patriotism among young people, increasing the activity of young people and their spiritual and moral education, and nurturing their socio-pedagogical abilities in the spirit of national development.

In foreign countries, the formation and development of civic competences in young people is instilled on the basis of the subject of «Civic Education». The subject of «Civic Education» instills in young people the foundations of building a civil society and a democratic state, since the social role of a citizen is manifested, first of all, in his participation in democratic processes and institutions. In particular, in Austria, the term «political education» is often used instead of «civic education». Frumin suggested using the concept of «democratic civic education» in his research, since in his research work he «implies the importance of developing and developing democratic mechanisms, not all values, skills and knowledge of a citizen». Summarizing the views of all the above scientists, we have explained the following pedagogical possibilities for developing socially active civic competence in students in a table format:

Pedagogical opportunities for developing socially active citizenship competence in students: instilling democratic values in students during the educational process (human dignity, generosity, peace in the country, humanity, freedom, patriotism), increasing the role of self-government bodies and civil society institutions in building a democratic society in the country, increasing students' initiative and activity, forming legal culture and legal awareness in students, developing knowledge and skills to participate in political processes as active citizens, developing socio-psychological, active citizenship qualities in students through democratic life experience, civic knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Because the development of socially active citizenship competence in students can be viewed as a condition for building a democratic legal state

and gradually increasing the social stability of society and its sustainable development.

Formation of socially active citizenship competencies in the general secondary education system of our country. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 187 dated April 6, 2017 «On Approval of State Educational Standards for General Secondary and Secondary Specialized, Vocational Education» sets the task of forming socially active citizenship competencies in students through the subjects «History», «Fundamentals of State and Law», «Constitutional Law», and «General Pedagogy», and the development of this formed competency in the higher education system plays an important role. The reforms being carried out in the education system in response to the new social changes being implemented in our country are showing their effectiveness. «Reform means renewal, change.

For reforms to yield positive results, first of all, our leaders and people must change. When people change, society changes. «Because, at the heart of any reform is the activity, initiative of our youth, and the support of their scientific and creative ideas, which indicates the prosperity of society tomorrow. Therefore, the development of socially active civic competence in students is the most important initiative factor in building justice, legal equality, a democratic state, and a civil society.

Social education is an important form of education, which means education that expresses a spiritual impact on the entire society, people, nation and class in accordance with the stated purpose. Social education is the process of forming and developing the consciousness and thinking of an individual, his spiritual and educational world in harmony and in harmony with the goals and objectives of society, the active participation of people in socio-economic and cultural life, a set of positive influences and factors. The main goal of social education is to unite citizens around a single national idea of mobilizing them to build a humane democratic society and a legal state. In social education, parental love, love of the Motherland, traditions of teacher-discipleship, national values, neighborhood and community control also have a great influence and are of great importance in the development of youth.

The intended goal can be achieved by creating an environment of active cooperation between «students of an educational institution and parents» in the social life of students, in the activities of initiative and volunteer groups, self-governing bodies, public organizations, «Talented Youth» science clubs, including through the development of student and parent councils.

The fact that the scientist in her research deeply analyzed the events and phenomena taking place in the political life of society in developing active citizenship qualities is also of great importance. S. Jurayeva, touching upon the issue of the younger generation, said: «The fact that young people feel responsible for the fate of the Motherland and the nation and feel a sense

of involvement in it» indicates that in any society, the upbringing of young people plays an important role in different eras.

A. Begmatov, who touched upon the importance of the humanistic principle in human education, said that personal activity in the educational process «if there is harmony between the interests of society and the interests of the individual, this situation encourages the individual to show selflessness in the interests of society, and therefore, through it, in the interests of his own interests.» A. Knyazev, who distinguished three stages of the formation of a person as a citizen, justifies the possibility of assessing civic competence as a result of the subject «Civic Education»:

- knowledge of a person’s civil rights and obligations and the history of the country;

- his system of attitude towards himself as a citizen, towards civil society and the state, towards civil rights and obligations;

- focuses on civic duty and citizen’s obligation, the interests of the state in civil society, the civic behavior of the individual; the civic values and beliefs of the individual. [3. p. 56]

The clarification of the development of socially active citizenship competencies in students as a socio-pedagogical necessity allowed us to highlight the following considerations:

- The main task of civil society in educating the younger generation is to develop socially active citizens;

- to ensure active social participation in all spheres of society by instilling in students the idea of building a democratic state;

- to ensure active participation of students in building a civil society, instilling in them the ideals of interethnic harmony, interreligious tolerance, national well-being, and the ideals of a perfect person; – to prepare students for independent life and develop their socio-political and legal literacy;

- to develop socially active citizenship competencies in students through active participation in social projects such as «Mentoring» and «Student Platform»;

- it is possible to develop socially active citizenship competencies of students in higher education institutions through «active participation in the activities of Youth Union associations, broad involvement in the activities of self-governing bodies.»

Therefore, the development of the subjective qualities of a person requires an individual approach to the development of civic competences, taking into account the purely individual assimilation of knowledge in the development of socially active citizenship competencies, the need to develop skills and competencies that depend on the subjective motives of learning, attitude to the subject of education, the abilities, personal qualities and experience of the learner.

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